

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF RMMC EMPLOYEES DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC: A PHENOMENOLOGY OF FORTITUDE

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Abstract: The purpose of this qualitative phenomenological study was to explore the experiences of RMMC employees during the COVID-19 pandemic for the school year 2021-2022. It also aimed to investigate the challenges encountered and their ways of coping with them. Ten female employees for the individual in-depth interview and another ten employees for the focused group discussion from this institution were involved in this endeavor. The results of the interview were transcribed and translated to produce core ideas and essential themes. As regards the description of lived experiences of RMMC employees during the COVID-19 pandemic the following were the essential themes: Life Became Difficult, Increased Worry, Faced Adjustment, Disrupted Normal Living, Disconnected, Deepen Covid-19 Awareness, Valued Health Consciousness, Stressful, Became Uncertain, Anxious, Frustrated, Disturbed, Challenged, Disappointed, Mixed-Emotion, Unproductive, Sad, Stressed, Happy, Grateful, At Ease, Vigilant, Employment is Still Good, Budgeting Became Necessary, Health Became Priority, Convenient Lifestyle, Embraced Change, Mentally Distracted, Negativity Increased, Adapted New Perspectives and Valued Each Moment. The study showed among others that the employees face several problems, difficulties, and challenges.

Keywords: Guidance and counseling, experiences, challenges, COVID-19 pandemic, non-teaching employees, fortitude, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Wherever you set on this continuum you will need to embrace rather than fight the uncertainty (Pringle, 2020). The passage explains that we are looking forward to coming out of lockdown and returning to the old normal. The current situation is tragic, heartbreaking, and filled with fear and anxiety. However, there are thin silver linings there if people look for them. It is our chance to reinvent and create a better world where we can all work, rest and play in the new normal. If we can find a way to embrace, adjust, and even become creative, we will get through the storm much better.

The Covid-19 pandemic then broke out, significantly impacting private college operations nationally and internationally. It has created a brand-new world of difficulties, choices, and possibilities. It is up to us to change and make the most of these obstacles to advance our nation and the rest of the world. Additionally, it has sparked a rare health crisis that has recently spread alarmingly. As a result, governments have been forced to implement drastic measures like population control and the suspension of in-person instruction (Ancheta, 2020; Gorna, MacDermott, Rayner, O'Hara, Evans, Agyen & Hastie, 2021).

Furthermore, the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic has been more than a disaster; it has served as a global wake-up call to shift our paradigms and perspectives. Not surprisingly, the epidemic has changed our perceptions of normalcy and how we live. Nonetheless, it is crucial to remember that one's new standard could be someone else's beginning (Bozcurt, Sharma & Karalis, 2020; Vaterlaus, Spruance & Patten, 2021).

Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic brought many disruptions to human life and livelihood in a way never preceding. The threats it has presented have affected one's physical and mental well-being or social and physical capital. In contrast, other threats have gone deep in raising questions inside an individual about his way of life and the reason for his existence. However, with these challenges still, many opportunities would bring new insights and inspiration to human life and the community. Believing in such possibilities would need both positive attitudes, which see the silver lining moments in these challenging times (Qiu et al., 2020; Tafazoli & Boroujeni, 2021).

However, people experience that during this pandemic era, life has become difficult. One feels unsafe when in contact with other people and hesitates to leave the house. People cannot do everyday things while being disconnected from other family and friends and financially unstable due to decreased salaries. This study aimed to explore the needs of the RMMC employees to overcome their worries, anxieties, and other panic disorder experiences. It is also envisioned to uplift them to stay braver, calmer, and happier amid the COVID-19 contagion.

This study aimed to determine how employees experienced the COVID-19 pandemic and the challenges they encountered. In this study, I focused on describing the lived experiences and challenges that arise for the RMMC employees during the COVID-19 pandemic and how they manage the situation. As a guidance facilitator, this study is beneficial for me to strengthen my capability to help and guide my clients to have a positive outlook during this difficult time.

Purpose of the study

This study aimed to describe the lived experiences of RMMC employees and investigate their challenges and ways of coping with the difficulties in handling clients during the COVID-19 pandemic.

A recorder was extensively used during the in-depth interview and the written comments gathered. Different assertions about the stories they plan to convey were grouped to form themes. These are the shared experiences of the participants. As a result of the in-depth interview, they could recall stories that would be used and recorded.

Moreover, the goal of qualitative study research is to help me to gain better knowledge and understanding of the lived experiences of RMMC employees. When people will read about this; they will be able to reflect on their lives and experiences and encourage them to understand their own lives better.

Research Questions

The researcher sought answers to the following questions:

1. How do the participants describe their lived experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic?
 - 1.1 How do the participants view their experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic?
 - 1.2 How do the participants feel about their experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic?
 - 1.3 How does the COVID-19 pandemic affect the participant's employment status and physical, mental, and emotional well-being?

Theoretical Lens

This present study was anchored on the three theories chosen for this study. The leading theory of this study is the PERMA Model Theory which is Positive Emotion, Engagement, Relationships, Meaning, and Accomplishment, designed by Martin Seligman (2002) with five core elements of psychological well-being and happiness. Seligman believes these five elements can help people achieve fulfillment, joy, and meaning. This positive view of life can help people in relationships and work and inspire them to be more creative and take more chances. This model can also be applied to institutions to develop programs to help people develop new cognitive and emotional tools.

In addition, the study was viewed from the theory of positive psychology. It is the scientific examination of the factors that make life most worthwhile. Positive psychology is a scientific method for examining human thoughts, feelings, and behavior. Additionally, it emphasizes strengths rather than weaknesses, builds on life's positive aspects rather than fixes its

negative ones, and transforms the lives of ordinary people into extraordinary ones rather than concentrating only on raising the standards of those struggling. Finally, positive psychology focuses on life's formative experiences and influences (Peterson 2008 & Ackerman 2020).

Last but not least, the Finding Meaning with Logotherapy theory is predicated on people's motivation to discover meaning and purpose in life. The meaning of life can be found in three different ways: by producing something or finishing a task; by fully experiencing something or loving someone; and by the perspective, one takes on inevitable suffering (Victor Frankl, 2012).

Significance of the Study

The result of this study benefits the following: *Globally Significance*, it can raise awareness about the different effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. This study aimed to assess the knowledge, preparedness, and wakefulness about preventive measures and disseminate appropriate information, which has a critical role in containing the disease to the *School Administrators*. They could use the result of the study to understand the present situations of the employees and enact procedures to sustain their mental well-being conditions. It also provides avenues for the employees to look at the problem from a more positive and hopeful perspective, to the *Employees*. The study's results would help them better understand the situation brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic to encourage them to remain strong and be positive despite the situation, which is unfavorable to all. It also allows employees to look at the situation more positively and with much hope.

Future Researchers. The information cited in the research paper will benefit future researchers conducting further studies. The study result can have the privilege of understanding the participants' experiences and, at the same time, will gain competence in the research procedures. *Proponent/Researcher*. The outcome of this study can help the researcher recommend mental health interventions to the administration that would help the employees sustain their positivity and resiliency during this era of the COVID-19 pandemic.

2. METHOD

The researcher used a qualitative type of research. According to Qualitative Research in Psychology, qualitative research collects information that is not in numerical form. For example, diary accounts, open-ended questionnaires, unstructured interviews, and unstructured observations. Qualitative research is useful for studies at the individual level and to find in-depth how people think or feel as to case studies (Jamshed, 2014).

A qualitative research design also offers the broadest range of acceptable methods and structures, making it the most adaptable of the different experimental techniques. Even though there is no set structure for this kind of study, it still needs to be carefully built and planned. Researchers must continuously ensure they use open-ended, bias-free methodologies and pay attention to possible sources of error. It typically entails deep sensitivity to the phenomenon in question and awareness of bias (Shuttleworth & Wilson, 2008; Denzin & Lincoln, 2012).

Also, qualitative research is an approach that explores and understands the meaning that individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem. Thus, the analysis and interpretation are negotiated with human data sources because they attempt to reconstruct the subjects' realities. He wrote about the various qualitative research designs. The phenomenological approach is best suited for research, in which it is essential to understand several individuals' common or shared experiences of a phenomenon. Therefore, the study used a phenomenological approach. The goals of qualitative phenomenological research are to describe a lived experience of a spectacle, to seek reality from people's narratives of their experiences and feelings, and to produce in-depth descriptions of the phenomenon. The methods used to analyze the data in this study must be quite different from more conventional or quantitative research methods because it is a qualitative analysis of narrative data (Creswell, 2014).

In addition, phenomenology is a reflective and inductive methodology. The phenomenological research method involves garnering insight into a person's lived experiences as they recollect them. Lived events and essences are a construct in phenomenological research. As the participant describes them, lived experiences are used to define the universal structures of the phenomenon. Lived events are how people live about a situation. Creswell wrote that of the various qualitative research designs, the phenomenological approach is best suited for research in which it is essential to understand several individuals' common or shared experiences of a phenomenon. Using this methodology, I sought to obtain and describe what participants experienced and how they experienced it (De Chesnay, 2014; Valge, 2018).

Similarly to this, phenomenological studies investigate human experiences based on the accounts offered by the participants. These encounters are referred to as lived experiences. Phenomenological research aims to explain the significance that experiences have for each subject. This kind of study is used to investigate subjects about which little is known (Donalek, 2004; Ivey, 2012; Tuffour, 2017).

Furthermore, in phenomenological research, participants are asked to describe their experiences as they perceive them. Although they might write about their experiences, the data is gathered through interviews in most cases. One must consider their beliefs and emotions to comprehend the lived experience from the subject's point of view. It must first specify what they anticipate finding before consciously putting those theories to the side; this is the process known as bracketing. It is possible to see the experience through the persons' eyes who have lived the experience when they set aside their thoughts about the phenomenon (Wilding & Whiteford, 2005).

In this study, For the inclusion criteria, for the individual in-depth interview must be ten female employees, employed at RMMC for three years and above, and they must be office personnel. There were five female and five male employees for the FGD. They have been employed at RMMC for three years and above and are still office personnel. For the exclusion criteria, all teaching personnel are not included even though they are affected by the pandemic. The office personnel who are busy people, like the finance and registrar, were not included because of the said criteria.

In the approval and verification of the rigor and appropriateness of the interview guide, the following data collection procedures were used:

First, I prepared the logistical requirements, such as the venue and audio/voice recorder used during the participant interviews. I selected the location and time during my initial meeting with the participants. Second, the participants were given a copy of the consent form to sign before the interview. It contained the study's aims, methodology, confidentiality, and advantages, as well as the researcher's contact information in case there were any questions or clarifications about the purpose. The consent form was then retrieved if there were no further queries or clarifications. After that, there was a Participant Agreement Form. It suggested that the participants and the researcher agree on how the interview and transcription procedure should be conducted. The form also asked for their consent to conduct the interview.

It was followed by a one-on-one interview with the participants strictly following health and safety protocols. It was divided into two parts. The initial section only requested information that would serve as the foundation for the participants' backgrounds. The second section of the interview comprised questions about their experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The one-on-one interview was conducted at a mutually agreed-upon time and location. The interview was recorded using a digital recorder. Their interview responses were transcribed following the interview process. After the interviews, I transcribed the audio recordings as quickly as feasible. The transcription was then shown to the participants to ensure the accuracy and dependability of the words. They signed their names beneath the transcription for credibility and validity (Chaleunvong, 2009 ;Wilson & Miller, 2014).

In data analysis in this study involved communicating the most important findings by condensing the material acquired and presenting the results. A data reduction technique, visualization, concluding, and verification, were used to assess the data (Hancock, Algozzine & Lim, 2021; Mezmir, 2020).

The data analysis process involved three steps. First, it is called analysis to break down a whole into its constituent parts for individual study. Data analysis takes raw data and turns it into information that users can use to make decisions. Finally, data were collected and examined to answer questions, test hypotheses, or disprove theories (Castleberry & Nolen, 2018; Tracy, 2019).

Further, the data were analyzed using interpretive phenomenological analysis (IPA) methodologies. The first interview, the first observation, and the first document accessed in the study all served as starting points for the research. The first step in an IPA analysis was to immerse oneself in the original data by reading and re-reading participant responses and making notes that reflected the researcher's initial impressions. Second, it involved finding and labeling themes that describe each text portion to reduce the data's detail volume. These titles are conceptual and should express the text's fundamental essence. Third, it involved searching for connections across identified themes and clustering them into structured pieces that made sense of the original data. Lastly, the researcher looked for patterns across interviews to integrate themes into an inclusive master list to summarize and understand the phenomenon of interest (MacLeod, 2019; Larkin, Shaw & Flowers, 2019).

3. RESULTS

Research question No 1: How do the participants view their experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic?

The following questions were asked during the in-depth interviews: 1. What can you say about the COVID-19 Pandemic?

2. How do you view yourself now that we are in this era of pandemic? Why do you say that?

3. In your experiences, what are the problems you meet most frequently during the COVID-19 pandemic?

4 How will you view your entire experiences during this time of pandemic? Tell me more about it?

5 How do your experiences influence your views about Covid-19 pandemic? Kindly cite your views on the impact of the pandemic?

From the data collected on the experiences of the study participants, nine major themes were generated as presented in Table 1. These themes presented the participants' view their experiences. The essential themes are described as (1) Life Become Difficult, (2) Increased Worry, (3) Face Adjustment, (4) Disruptive Normal Living, (5) Disconnected, (6) Deepened Covid-19 Awareness, (7) Valued Health Consciousness, (8) Stressful, and (9) Became Uncertain.

Research Question No. 2: How do the participants feel about their experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic?

The following questions were asked during the in-depth to find out the feelings about their experiences during the pandemic:

1. As an employee of this institution, how does it feel to be affected by the pandemic? Why did you say that?

2. What do you feel when doing your job at home? Tell me more in detail.

3. Are there times that you feel frustrated about work during these time of uncertainties? Why do you say that?

4. How do you feel about when you were not able to accomplish something in your work because of the threat of the pandemic?

5. What were the emotions you felt due to the Covid-19 pandemic? Why do you say so?

6. What was your feeling when you had the skeletal reporting in the workplace because of this issue? What makes you say that?

7. What did you feel when you only received 70% of your salary during the pandemic? Why did you say that?

8. Was there a time you felt that the school would resort to closure due to the pandemic? How did it impact you? Tell me about it.

9. What was the feeling of being deprived of some rights like enjoying the conversion of our Vacation Leave (which was not used) into cash? Tell me in detail.

10. How did these feelings change the different aspect of your life? Tell me further.

From the data collected on the comprehensions of the study participants, fourteen major themes emerged as presented in Table 2. These themes present the feelings about their experiences during the pandemic of the participants. The essential themes are defined as (1) Anxious, (2) Frustrated, (3) Disturbed, (4) Challenged, (5) Disappointed, (6) Mixed-Emotion, (7) Unproductive, (8) Sad, (9) Stressed, (10) Happy, (11) Grateful, (12) At Ease, (13) Positive, and (14) Vigilant.

Research Question No. 3: How does covid-19 pandemic affect the participant's employment status, physical, mental and emotional well- being?

The following questions were asked during the in-depth to find out the affect of the participants' aspect during the pandemic:

1. Does Covid-19 pandemic affect your employment status? Why did you say that?

2. How does it affect your physical aspect? Why do you say so?

3. How does it affect your mental aspect? Why do you say so?

4. How does it affect your emotional well-being? Why do you say so?

5. What were the opportunities you experienced during the Pandemic?

6. What were the challenges you experienced during the COVID-19 pandemic? How did you cope with these challenges?
7. How does the pandemic change your life? Why do you say so?
8. After all, how does the COVID-19 make you realize? Tell me more about it.

From the data collected on the insights of the study participants, nine major themes emerged as presented in Table 3. These themes present the effect of the participant's employment status, physical, mental and emotional well-being. The essential themes are described as (1) Employment Is Still Good, (2) Budget Became Necessary, (3) Health Became Priority (4) Convenient Lifestyle, (5) Embrace Change, (6) Mentally Distracted, (7) Negativity Increased, (8) Adapted New Perspective and (9) Value Each Moment.

Based on the responses of the in-depth interview informants the following data were gathered:

On the experience of the participants, nine themes emerged to describe their view during the COVID-19 pandemic. These themes are namely, (a) Life Become Difficult, (b) Increased Worry, (c) Face Adjustment, (d) Disruptive Normal Living, (e) Disconnected, (f) Deepened Covid-19 Awareness, (g) Valued Health Consciousness, (h) Stressful, and (i) Became Uncertain. In relation to the Life Become Difficult, the results of this study have shown that participants experienced hard, fatal health crises, worries, suffering, devastation, and death that led to their life becoming difficult. Increased Worry, the participants are experiencing increased worry about their safety, afraid of communicating with people, financial instability, fear of dying, keep on thinking about the virus, and job insecurity. For the, faced adjustment comes in when the participants tried hard to adjust to the new normal, adopted modern technology, became more resourceful, adapted to social distancing, strived hard to follow proper health protocol, and changed their mindset. The disrupted normal living, the impact of the pandemic led to the participant's changes in their daily routine, struggling with limited movement, hassle wearing facemasks and face shields, becoming over thinkers, crises arising in the educational arena, afflicted people, and quarantine brought great devastation. Disconnected, they could not see distant family members, which caused the participants to be disconnected. Socialization was prohibited, communication became challenging, and they could not visit sick family members. Also, deepen Covid-19 awareness, the best way to prevent and slow transmission is to be well-informed about the disease and how the virus spreads and lastly valued health consciousness is evident to the participants in taking extra care of themselves and following proper health protocol to avoid virus transmission, and safety became a priority. Everyone reacts differently to stressful situations such as an infectious disease outbreak and became uncertain about the future became unclear.

The participants feeling about their experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic: fourteen significant themes generated from it, (a) Anxious, (b) Frustrated, (c) Disturbed, (d) Challenged, (e) Disappointed, (f) Mixed-Emotion, (g) Unproductive, (h) Sad, (i) Stressed, (j) Happy, (k) Grateful, (l) At Ease, (m) Positive, and (n) Vigilant.

The participants describe their positive and negative feelings, making them anxious, frustrated, disturbed, disappointed, unproductive, sad, and stress. It causes the participants to be worried about being unemployed, fearful of acquiring the virus and getting infected, fearing financial matters, anxious about their job status, and concerned about the bills and budget. The COVID-19 Pandemic has had a significant effect on our lives. As a result, many of us are facing challenges that can be stressful and overwhelming. Besides, happy, grateful, at ease, positive and vigilant. Happiness comes in when the participants are glad of new opportunities, appreciate the admin's initiative, are happy due to less exposure, can do the job and spend time with family, also increases the employees' resiliency during this time of the pandemic. It provides an avenue for the employees to look at the situation from a more positive and hopeful perspective.

In terms of the participant's employment status, physical, mental and emotional well-being, nine significant themes emerged from it, (a) Employment Is Still Good, (b) Budget Became Necessary, (c) Health Became Priority (d) Convenient Lifestyle, (e) Embrace Change, (f) Mentally Distracted, (g) Negativity Increased, (h) Adapted New Perspective and (i) Value Each Moment.

It was shown that during the pandemic did not significantly affect the employment status of the employees. Nothing changed despite the challenges brought by the pandemic, they are thankful to have work still, and the institution found means to support the employees. The pandemic has turned the participants to have proper budgeting, becoming prudent, learning to save money, and saving for emergency funds, which is excellent because they have something to spend in times of emergency. Adapting the new usual way of life, especially learning to be open-minded, accepted the new typical scenario and everyday things were no longer practiced. They no longer operate similarly regarding how we know, work, and live. Every aspect of their daily lives is impacted, and this new normal appeared almost immediately. Life changes can be

challenging and elicit a wide range of feelings. Agility and an open mind are necessary to transition to a new normal. The COVID-19 pandemic has made the participants to keep thinking negative things, experiencing sadness, being emotionally disturbed, and experiencing a lot of downfalls. They cannot do everyday things like before, and the different restrictions or lockdowns lead to stress. This negative feeling changes participants' lives, which could affect their employment and limitations. Participants value life as much as they love their health, especially that of their loved ones. They take good care of one's physical, mental, and emotional well-being and show respect for others and life.

4. DISCUSSION

The researcher chose the qualitative research method, particularly phenomenology since her study involved human perceptions based on their experiences. Stan Lester (2007) believed that the goal of the phenomenological approach is to shed light on particular phenomena by identifying them according to how the participants in a situation perceive them. This typically translates into obtaining "deep" knowledge and perceptions about people using inductive, qualitative techniques like interviews, discussions, and participant observation and then representing them from the viewpoint of the research subject (s). All 20 informants were asked to participate and share their challenges as employees in RMMC. As well as their viewpoints and perceptions of what they have been through. All participants were from General Santos City. The results of this study were based on the actual experiences of the non-teaching employees within the school community thirty one essential themes emerged:

Life Became Difficult. The following are key terms that led to the participants' life becoming difficult: misery, complex, fatal, health crisis, worried, suffering, devastation, and death. It brought difficulty to everyone due to the life-changing adjustment in our usual way of living. It is thinking about the viruses in our surroundings that affect our health. According to Bozcourt, Sharma, & Karalis (2020), as a result, people were affected by the pandemic because it impacted their daily lives. The coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic has been more than a disaster; it has served as a global wake-up call to shift our paradigms and perspectives. Not surprisingly, the epidemic has changed our perceptions of normalcy and how we live.

Increased worry about the safety of their family members and stressed their financial needs. Anxiety and fear are natural protectors of participants' lives. These reactions set off the fight-or-flight response, which drives people to behave in a primal manner by either running away or engaging in combat. In spite of the numerous threats in this world, this reaction has kept humans alive for generations. These outcomes line up with those of the World Health Organization (2020). The COVID-19 pandemic has caused a shocking loss of life on a global scale and poses an unprecedented threat to food systems, employment, and public health. Tens of millions of people are at risk of living in extreme poverty as a result of the pandemic's economic and social disruption, and the number of undernourished people, which is currently estimated to be close to 690 million, could rise by as many as 132 million by the end of the year.

Faced Adjustment. Perceived limitations in everyday life, the safety of everyone, and our daily routines during the COVID-19 pandemic phases have been drastically reduced. During the pandemic, the participants faced adjustments to reduce their frequency of going out and their need to engage in unhealthy behaviors at home. Taking care of their health has attracted the participants' attention. The pandemic has turned the participants to save money, which is excellent, especially during an emergency, just like what we are experiencing nowadays. On the same note, Ichiro (2020) wrote that individually we could start with just one or two good new actions or behaviors. Then, we can each build these into positive habits. These can help to make us more adaptable and resilient. We can then have confidence in our choices and plans and help others obtain the assistance they need. In that way, we will all be in a better place in our new communities.

Disrupted Normal Living. The restrictions caused by coronavirus are dramatically affecting how participants live their everyday life, which may change their daily routine, struggles with limited movement, and the hassle of wearing facemasks and face shields. The changes in times do not mean we must let go of the things that matter to us. It is a matter of re-thinking how we can adapt the everyday living. The study was supported by Sistema (2020), that the global outbreak of the pandemic has spread worldwide, affecting almost all countries and territories. Hand washing, wearing face masks, keeping a physical distance, and avoiding large gatherings and assemblies have all been public health precautions. To flatten the curve and stop the spread of the disease, lockdown and homebound strategies have been implemented.

Disconnected. The restrictions caused by coronavirus are dramatically affecting how participants live their everyday life, which may change their daily routine, struggles with limited movement, and the hassle of wearing facemasks and face shields. The changes in times do not mean we must let go of the things that matter to us. It is a matter of re-thinking how we can adapt the everyday living. The study was supported by Sistema (2020), that the global outbreak of the pandemic has spread worldwide, affecting almost all countries and territories. Hand washing, wearing face masks, keeping a physical

distance, and avoiding large gatherings and assemblies have all been public health precautions. To flatten the curve and stop the spread of the disease, lockdown and homebound strategies have been implemented.

Deepen Covid-19 Awareness. The virus is characterized by rapid transmission and can occur by close contact with an infected person. Participants deepen COVID-19 awareness to become more vigilant, equipped their selves with the virus, and become knowledgeable on the effect of a pandemic. In the study of Alonso & Benavente et al. (2020), people may gain awareness and knowledge about the disease and its transmission via television, news, and media platforms to protect themselves and their families. The crisis has resulted in an unprecedented impact on societies worldwide. Most of the world's population has been compelled to drastically alter the behavior patterns they had previously thought to be automatic or standard for a number of daily activities. Many nations issued various measures and stay-at-home instructions during the pandemic's peak.

Valued Health Consciousness. It caused a global change in the lifestyles of people around the world. Valuing life as the participants value their health, especially their loved ones. Taking extra care of oneself, following proper health protocol, and safety became a priority of the participants. On the same note, Alini, Harahap, Irfan & Febria (2020) state that the issue of the pandemic is very shocking to the world. It has altered the pattern of human life toward a new life order. This new life order requires the health consciousness of every human being. Everyone has the consciousness of something that happens in his/her life, one of which is health consciousness. The individual with health consciousness is shown to be constantly active and consistent in behaving daily, seeking information about health and its prevention, and always being motivated to be healthy. With the pandemic, many societies have begun to realize the importance of health following their respective levels of consciousness.

Stressful conditions, such as an infectious illness outbreak, cause diverse reactions in various people. It is common to feel a variety of emotions. For example, during an infectious disease outbreak, participants may experience emotions of insecurity, burden, restricted mobility, and financial instability. Their anxiety levels may also rise due to their financial situation, physical condition, or concern about contracting the virus. In a study by Umucu and Lee (2020), the COVID-19 pandemic is a worldwide public health emergency affecting people physically and psychologically. Hence, many people have been experiencing stress, anxiety, depression, low sleep quality, mood alterations, and high levels of posttraumatic stress disorder symptomatology.

Became Uncertain. Even though there is a lot of uncertainty in life and people worry about the future and there are many things that are still out of their control, having the right mindset can help people deal with challenging situations and confidently face the unknown, especially during this pandemic. Participants are perplexed by what life has to offer; the future seems hazy, navigating daily tasks is difficult, and it's unclear when the virus will stop. Every one of us has different levels of tolerance for uncertainty in life. While some people seem to enjoy taking chances and leading unpredictable lives, others find the arbitrary nature of life to be incredibly upsetting. We all, however, have a limit. The present study supports the stance of Zavras (2020) that during the period of the pandemic, most of these sources have contributed to the high degree of global uncertainty in the context of the pandemic's physical, psychological, financial, and social impacts. Uncertainty is therefore related not only to the seriousness of the threats to people's physical health and lives, the lack of early knowledge about quarantine duration, the real risk of exposure, and the unpredictability of symptomatology, but also to the impacts on personal, economic, and societal levels. Thus, uncertainty arises from various aspects of the crisis.

Anxious. It brought feelings of anxiety to the participants, which could affect their job status, fear of acquiring the virus, afraid of financial matters, and worry about the bills and budget. Many of us are dealing with difficulties that may cause stress or even feel overwhelming. People and those around us will become more resilient if we can learn healthy stress management techniques. Anxiety is a typical response to danger and uncertain situations. For many of us, the coronavirus illness creates a very uncertain future, claims Wnuk (2020). Both domestically and internationally, people are concerned about their own and their loved ones' health. A person's financial situation, their capacity to engage in important social and community activities, their ability to participate in meaningful hobbies, as well as other important aspects of their lives, may also be a major source of concern.

Frustrated. The pandemic's impact is that most participants feel frustrated because the adjustment is not so easy due to the inability to finish tasks because of the changes with the limited resources, getting annoyed by the virus carrier, and getting frustrated with the work. On the same note, Forshaw, Makridis, Rothwell & Thomson (2020) state that there is a draining sense of hopelessness that things will never return to the way they were before the pandemic. Others who are immune compromised or at high risk for severe may have lived in fear of dying or getting sick. Many feel the mental toll of isolation

and the strain of constantly adapting to new rules, new ways of doing things, and new realities. An unpredictable event occurs, leading to many other unpredictable consequences (as to changes in the reality of everyday life). Thus, unexpected pandemic changes occur at many levels of human existence. However, the most basic level in everyday life requires constantly reproducing practices and satisfying individual and collective needs.

Disturbed. The pandemic may have brought many changes to how people live their lives. With it, at times, the participants were mentally disturbed, worried about the continuous spread of the virus, bothered by the parent's decision to continue education, and nervous that everyone might have the virus. However, people can expect their intense feelings to fade when the pandemic is over and increase their ability to cope with life's ongoing challenges. According to Husky, Li, Luo, & Patsali (2020), students are coping with the emotional effects of a pandemic in addition to stressors associated with a potentially unfamiliar online learning environment. Areas hardest hit at the start of the pandemic, such as nations in Asia and Europe, are where a large portion of the initial research on the coronavirus' effects on mental health originates. According to this study, disruptions brought on by contagion and its effects have significantly raised college students' levels of stress, anxiety, depression, and suicidality.

Challenged. During the acute phase of the pandemic, participants were challenged with limited interaction and different modalities, striving hard to come up with solutions, difficulty collaborating with colleagues, and the crisis significantly affected the education sector. As stated in the study of Greenstone & Nigam (2020), the enormous scale of the crisis and its impact are naturally causing a lot of fear, uncertainty, and anxiety across the globe. Because it is difficult to predict how the pandemic will play out and because things are changing so quickly, it is particularly stressful. Furthermore, along with the current spread of the virus, physical distancing and face masks wearing in public and private college schools are compulsory once classes are resumed or started. Governments worldwide have issued policies and guidelines to implement physical distancing to flatten the pandemic curve. Furthermore, wearing facemasks or even personal protective equipment (PPE) as a public health intervention would likely intercept the transmission link and prevent infectious infections.

Feeling disappointed arose and changed the participants' lives with unfinished work and dissatisfaction because their access to information was limited, and they were dismayed by having low computer literacy. These results correspond with Finney (2020). As the coronavirus pandemic brings the country to a standstill, many of our everyday activities and even unique, once-in-a-lifetime milestones are being postponed or changing in ways we never expected. Important milestones like weddings, graduations, birthday parties, and funerals are postponed or canceled due to the coronavirus pandemic. It is natural to feel disappointed, sad, or even angry about this. Check-in with yourself and see how people are feeling. Recognizing and owning their feelings is the first step on the path to acceptance of the situation. Life should be in pencil with a big eraser. Avoid making significant life changes during this stressful but temporary time. Think through all their options before making personal or business decisions. Quick action may feel good when we are anxious, but holding steady may be the best choice.

Mixed Emotion. Participants simultaneously experienced positive and negative emotions such as feeling tired, happy, challenged because of the new normal, had anxiety and stressed but still blessed, happy but struggling with the spread of the virus, physically tired, exhausted and had fatigue, and glad yet devastated by some changes, sick, mentally anxious but still hopeful. Accordingly, Schelhorn, Schluter, & Paintner (2020) found that several studies conducted since the pandemic's start revealed a concerning rise in depression and anxiety disorders, general distress, and sleep disorders, as well as a worsening of the already-present symptoms of posttraumatic stress disorder, depression, and eating disorders. Since emotions, emotional episodes, moods, and dispositional states are all balanced states that people experience in response to a pandemic, positive and negative affective states, defined here as the superordinate categories for those states, are relevant.

Unproductive. During a pandemic, Boateng & Doku (2020), said that the fear of the spread and lethality of a disease can create anxiety, stress, and depression with a lasting psychological impact on the overall health and well-being of the population. As a result, many countries imposed various preventive measures, including social distancing, isolation measures, and mandatory self-quarantine for persons who traveled from affected countries or those suspected to have been in contact with exposed or infected persons. However, while these containment measures might have contributed to the protection of the public's health, they have implications for mental health outcomes such as anxiety, stress, boredom, negative religious coping, extreme hopelessness, suicidal ideation, and the well-being of populations at the individual, household, and community levels.

Sad. The COVID-19 pandemic had a significant effect on our lives. Many people face challenges that can be stressful. We sad for clients such as students and parents. The budget was cut short. People felt miserable with the responsibilities like paying many bills, feeling down because vacation leave was not converted into cash, worried due to the financial crisis, and

feeling sad about not performing well at school. The present study supports the stance of Ustun (2021) that it is normal to have stress, anxiety, sadness, and fear in times like these. The coronavirus crisis is unlike anything we have experienced before. One of the scariest things is uncertainty. Everything keeps changing. When it feels like things might be getting better, they seem to get worse again. Human beings hate uncertainty and want guaranteed answers. Because there are not any and because it sometimes feels like there is so much different information flying around, our anxiety is often likely to be high. Again, this is the most normal thing in the world right now.

Stressful situations, like an infectious disease outbreak, cause different reactions in different people. It is common to feel a variety of emotions. Participants experienced stress as a result of the uncertainty surrounding the start of classes, the lack of certainty regarding when the virus will be eradicated, and the administration's policies. Wnuk (2020) states that stress is an understandable response to the coronavirus pandemic. People might be worried about catching the virus, how their loved ones will cope, the disruption to their studies and routines, and whether people will still have a job and enough money. These stressors include the constant media hysteria and disappointment, such as travel bans, canceled events, and other activities.

Happiness comes when the participants can spend time with their families, are glad of new opportunities, appreciate the admin's initiative, and with less exposure to people with viruses. In the context of the study of Falcone 2020; American Heart Association News (2020), revealed that happiness motivates individual activities, raises awareness, strengthens creativity, and facilitates social relationships. It is vitally important, especially at this time of the pandemic. No one exactly knows when the pandemic will end. Happiness is a field of study known as positive psychology, so it has a broad and defined content area and is well-researched. To be happy is not so simple, especially amid coronavirus worries, but it is perfect for health.

Grateful. Our faith may be tested during such unsure times, and it may be difficult to understand how God fits into our lives. Participants felt thankful for everything, became more appreciative of the value of life, grateful for the protection of the Lord, blessed for the support of family, and thankful for still having a job. On the same note, Gordon (2020) states that in many places worldwide, the pandemic means perpetually living under the gun. The pandemic can feel overwhelming due to new information, long work hours, and caring for one's family. It is crucial to take a moment to gather one's thoughts because global pandemics can be stressful and can be mitigated by maintaining composure. One of the oldest ideas in society is the idea of giving thanks and expressing gratitude. Even in the midst of difficult, demanding, and overwhelming circumstances, it serves as a reminder of how unique, lovely, and blessed our lives are.

At Ease. The coronavirus makes participants feel safer to stay at home, relieved because the school is not reducing the workforce or the collaborative effort of both employees and administration is significant in this time of pandemic to find the means to continue the operation of the institution to surpass and adopt the new normal, at ease because the exposure was limited and become more comfortable to work at home. Fontanarosa & Bauchner (2020) state that the pandemic is impacting humankind in unprecedented and monumental ways, and data is needed to plan for the next steps following the acute outbreak. In addition to physical health, coping with the pandemic requires mental resilience. Tools have been established to estimate resilience, broadly conceptualized as healthy and adaptive functioning in the aftermath of adversity. Measuring resilience can allow better resource allocation planning and inform interventions for individuals and communities to overcome the acute pandemic effects expected to impact mental health. Healthcare providers are at the frontlines of the pandemic response and already show deleterious mental health consequences. Hence, there is an urgent need to gauge the role of resilience to achieve a worry-free situation amid the pandemic.

Positive. The pandemic gives a positive outlook in life for the participants to become more understanding of the situation, more open to opportunities, adjusted to the proper health protocol, keep on praying to survive, become more resourceful, choose to collaborate, help one another, and adjust to the online classes. Soklaridis, Lin, Lalani, Rodak & Sockalingam (2020), stated that believing in such opportunities would need both positive attitudes and seeing the silver lining of these challenging times. Calls have been made to address the public crisis related to mental illness as the global health crisis continues to spread across the globe. By taking into account the role that beneficial psychological traits can play in protecting against mental illness, supporting mental health during a pandemic, and developing beneficial processes and capacities that may help to strengthen future mental health, the current paper aims to broaden these calls.

Vigilant. The disease has been a part of our daily lives. To prevent this, participants wore facemasks and face shields, took extra care of themselves, strictly followed proper health protocol, were more concerned about the family's health, and were vigilant of the people around them. According to Westrupp & Youssef (2020), everyone is responsible for practicing

physical distancing, frequent hand washing, cough/sneeze etiquette, proper tissue usage and disposal, avoiding touching their face, adhering to quarantine/isolation protocols, and respecting others. People all over the country have taken precautions to stay safe since the COVID-19 outbreak started. Furthermore, it is crucial to continue taking those precautions until the virus is under control and a vaccine is available to shield everyone from contracting it. It is important to keep in mind that the virus primarily spreads from person to person, especially if two people are within six feet of one another. Additionally, keep in mind that even those who are symptom-free can still have the virus and spread it.

Employment is Still Good. Participants felt blessed that the employment status is still good, the school finds a means to support the employees, nothing changed despite the challenges brought by the pandemic, and they are thankful to have work still. Gordon (2020) states that one of society's oldest ideas is giving thanks and expressing gratitude. Even amid complex, demanding, and overwhelming circumstances, it reminds us how unique, lovely, and blessed our lives are. The idea of gratitude is crucial amid a pandemic like COVID-19 when the world is unpredictable and occasionally even dangerous, and if people are curious about how gratitude can affect their lives or look for ways to incorporate more appreciation and thankfulness into their daily lives.

Budgeting Became Necessary. The financial challenges brought about by the pandemic to the participants are proper budgeting, becoming prudent, and learning to save money for an emergency fund. On the same note, Holz (2020) states that the world is uncertain, which can cause fear and even panic. When people panic, they make less-than-optimal choices, but we can fight back against these urges. One of the best ways to feel more in control is by saving money. Building up a stash of cash can give us choices when we feel like everything else is falling apart. At the very least, it can help us feel less anxious about one crucial element of our lives. As places and activities shut down around us to protect us from the coronavirus, this presents us with a multifaceted opportunity. Fewer things to do gives us fewer things to spend our money on.

Health Became a Priority. During the pandemic, the participants reduced their frequency of going out and their need to engage in unhealthy behaviors. Taking care of their health has attracted the participants' attention, such as vaccination, spraying alcohol, following proper health protocol always, becoming more conscious of health, learning to take good care of the body and getting enough sleep, and staying healthy. The study presented by Alini, Harahap, Irfan, & Febria (2020), states that the issue is very shocking to the world. Moreover, it has altered the pattern of human life toward a new life order. This new life order requires the health consciousness of every human being. Everyone is conscious of something that happens in their life, one of which is health consciousness. The individual with health consciousness is shown to be constantly active and consistent in behaving daily, seeking information about health and its prevention, and always being motivated to be healthy.

Convenient Lifestyle. Realizing that no matter how much we consider we have, just at the end of the day, the members came to value having spent more quality time with the family is appreciating life. They preferred to study at home, believed that home was the safest place, and got the chance to attend webinars. Sabo (2020) expounded that being a homebody is mandatory in addition to a convenient lifestyle for many of us. Many states have issued stay-at-home orders for the foreseeable future to contain the spread of coronavirus. That means many families are spending more time together than they usually do. All that togetherness can present challenges, mainly because everyone is confined and in close quarters. However, people can do plenty to make the most of family time together. Consider that family bonding is an investment in everyone's health.

Embraced Change. Perceived limitations in everyday life, the safety of everyone, and our daily routines during the pandemic phases have been drastically reduced. Participants learned to be open-minded, accepted the new standard scenario, and everyday things were no longer practiced. Pringle (2020) wrote that in some ways, the changes in 2020 that have been forced on us are similar. Some have said that the virus's uncertainty is the hardest to handle. People can only predict what the future will hold. Today, as we encounter yet another "new normal," we have a choice: either accept it and adapt, or we can dig in and obstinately resist it, longing for the days gone by. Fighting it will not help and will not accomplish anything. People have often outpaced their rivals by one step. We can attempt it again because it has been done before, and people have survived. We will weather the storm much better if we learn to accept, adapt, and be creative. Many schools, colleges, and universities accepted their "new normal through the summer term." Many people have been busy developing and introducing brand-new online teaching and learning techniques. Churches have provided Sunday services and Bible studies on Zoom. Our "new normal" could consist of embracing creativity and having fun. Unfortunately, some of us are still having trouble adjusting to change. We have no control over the situations we find ourselves in, but we do have control over how we react to them.

Mentally Distracted. The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted our lives. Many of us are dealing with complex and overwhelming challenges. The participants have reported experiencing mental diversion due to the pandemic, including increased environmental anxiety, worry about contracting an infection, inability to concentrate at work, worry about money, and fear of interacting with others and leaving the house. Concerning life post-pandemic, what Petsanis (2020) worries about most is mental health. Mental health repercussions regarding what is happening during this pandemic for people, today and beyond, will be a problem in general, Petsanis said. In general, stressful behavior brings many issues to many people. He sees mental health warning signs throughout the population.

Negativity Increased. Negative things came in when the participants experienced sadness, were emotionally disturbed, experienced many downfalls, and affected psychological and mental health. It brought about many changes in people's daily routines, including uncertainty, altered daily routines, financial strains, and social isolation occasionally. People might be concerned about contracting an illness, how long the pandemic will last, whether it will affect their job, and what the future holds. Their life may seem out of control and make them unsure of what to do due to information overload, rumors, and incorrect information. It was evident in the study of Rezapour, Dehzangi, & Saadati (2020) that countries around the world have responded to curb the spread of the virus by imposing strict measures such as a lockdown or social distancing. This situation has led to changes in education systems, so schools and colleges have been subjected to different adjustments and closings in more than 180 countries. Although strict measures such as social distancing are required to contain the spread of the disease, it impacts individuals in terms of their habits, lifestyles, and how they see things during this pandemic.

Adapted New Perspectives. How we live, work, and learn has fundamentally changed due to adapting to the new normal. Each element of our daily lives is impacted, and this new normal has emerged almost overnight. Life changes can be challenging and elicit a wide range of feelings. Agility and an open mind are necessary to transition to a new normal. Participants developed selflessness, worked harder to overcome obstacles in life, armed themselves with optimism, increased their prayerfulness, and improved their interpersonal connections. Corpuz (2020) once said that we have suddenly been forced to adjust to the new typical work-from-home setting a year after the COVID-19 pandemic first surfaced. Lockdown and quarantine, the requirement to wear face masks and shields in public, and parents homeschooling their kids in an innovative blended learning environment are all examples of these. Many people have already designated 2020 as the worst year of the twenty-first century.

Valued Each Moment. It caused a global change in the lifestyles of people around the world. Participants appreciate each other more, enjoy life to the fullest, take care of physical, mental, and emotional health, become more loving and caring, and value life and the people around them more. Tennyson (2020) has taught us that the world will never be the same again, no matter what anyone's nationality, color, gender, creed, and faith is. We must agree that we are learning a new way of life that will become the norm. The old order changed, yielding place to new, are so apt. Nevertheless, we do not have to be scared that everything will come to an end. Some will indeed succumb to the battle. It is equally saddening to see the plight of the poor. It is not even appropriate to categorize the present situation as a boon or bane. We must be sensible, cautious, pragmatic, and optimistic to sail through. Man no longer needs complicated philosophy for life.

Implications for Practice

Based on the findings, the following implications for practice are presented. In the experiences of the RMMC employees, thirty-two significant themes were generated: Life Become Difficult, Increased Worry, Face Adjustment, Disruptive Normal Living, Disconnected, Deepened Covid-19 Awareness, Valued Health Consciousness, Stressful, Became Uncertain, Anxious, Frustrated, Disturbed, Challenged, Disappointed, Mixed-Emotion, Unproductive, Sad, Stressed, Happy, Grateful, At Ease, Positive, Vigilant, Employment Is Still Good, Budget Became Necessary, Health Became Priority Convenient Lifestyle, Embrace Change, Mentally Distracted, Negativity Increased, Adapted New Perspective and Value Each Moment.

Life Become Difficult. These brought difficulty to everyone because of life-changing adjustments in our usual way of living, we think about the viruses that affect our health. Self-care strategies are suitable for mental and physical health and can help take charge of employees' life. First, be mindful of physical health. It includes getting enough sleep, participating in regular physical activity, meditation, walking outside, painting, gardening, cooking, eating a healthy meal, relaxing, recharging and focusing on positive thoughts, using their moral compass or spiritual life for support, and making connections that encourage them to remain strong and optimistic despite the situation, which is unfavorable to all (Scott & Goldman, 2022).

Increased Worry. Increased worry about the safety of the family members and feeling stressed over financial necessities. Fear and anxiety serve as built-in life protectors for participants. They must therefore make time for their favorite activities. Make something, whether a new recipe, a craft, or an original piece of art, or read good books, watch comedies, play fun boards, or video games. It does not matter what people do as long as it takes them out of their worries (Limcaoco, Mateos, Fernández & Roncero, 2020).

Face Adjustment. Perceived limitations in everyday life, the safety of everyone, and our daily routines during the pandemic phases have been drastically reduced. The employees faced adjustments to reduce their frequency of going out and their need to engage in unhealthy behaviors at home. They must look at this by considering that to win the war against COVID-19. They need to make sacrifices and develop a coping mindset such as adjusting their expectations, giving their selves a break, being more kind and patient, and practicing acceptance of viewing life with a positive outlook (Cheng, Lam & Leung, 2022).

Disruptive Normal Living. Coronavirus restrictions are having a significant impact on participants' daily lives. These limits may create adjustments to routines, struggle with restricted movement, and cause inconvenience from wearing facemasks and face shields. The changing times do not need us to give up the important things for us; instead, we need to reconsider how we might adjust our way of life. We must establish a new routine and add new exercises and activities, like journaling. Set aside time to video call or phone others, be with someone through walking meditations, connect not only with others but also with others, and begin and end the day positively (Zhang, Wang, Rauch & Wei, 2020).

Disconnected. Participants experience being disconnected from their relatives, friends, and even their sick family and limited socialization outside. These are typical encounters when someone adjusts to any significant shift in life. Finding strategies and maintaining a routine, even if people are stuck at home, try to stick to their regular sleep, meal, or work schedule. It can help people maintain a sense of normalcy (Li, 2022).

Deepen Covid-19 Awareness. The virus is characterized by rapid transmission and can occur by close contact with an infected person. Therefore, participants deepen COVID-19 awareness to become more vigilant, equipped their selves with the virus, and become knowledgeable on the effect of a pandemic. In addition, to advocate the essential preventive measures for the employees, including practicing good hygiene, supported by physical distancing (avoid direct physical contact by hugging, touching, or shaking hands), reducing managing work-related travel, and regular environmental cleaning and disinfection. Knowledge and awareness of the disease are essential parameters for adopting protective measures that minimize the exposure risk of the illness (Capasso, Kim, Ali, Jones, DiClemente & Tozan, 2022).

Valued Health Consciousness. Valuing life as the employees value their health, especially their loved ones. Therefore, taking extra care of oneself, followed by proper health and safety protocol, became a priority. Maintain a healthy lifestyle of exercise, meditation, and regular sleep. Eat at home to avoid contact with other people and reduce the chance of being exposed to covid-19 (Al-Hosan, AlRajeh & Arnout, 2020).

Stressful. Stressful conditions, such as an infectious illness outbreak, cause diverse reactions in various people. It is usual to feel a variety of emotions. For example, during an infectious disease outbreak, participants may experience emotions of insecurity, burden, restricted mobility, and financial instability. Their anxiety levels may also rise due to their financial situation, physical condition, or concern about contracting the virus. Taking up relaxation techniques such as deep breathing, meditation, and yoga can bring people back into a state of equilibrium. However, regular practice delivers the most significant benefits, so see if they can set aside even a little time daily (Kar, 2021).

Became Uncertain. Furthermore, life is fraught with uncertainty and fears about the future. While many things remain outside one's control, thinking is vital to coping with adverse circumstances and discreetly facing the unknown, especially at this pandemic moment. Participants struggle with what life delivers; the future becomes unknown, everyday life is tough to achieve, and it is unsure when the virus will cease. We are all different in how much uncertainty we can tolerate in life. Some people like taking risks and living unpredictable lives, while others find the randomness of life unsettling. However, all of us have a limit. Stability rocks are grounding and help people to remember that some things are within their control. When certain aspects of one's life are disrupted, one's routines and rituals become extremely important. Some examples of stability rocks could be waking up every day at the same time, eating regular meals, going to bed at the same time, doing some form of exercise every morning, and reaching out to a friend each day (Koffman, Gross, Etkind & Selman, 2020).

Anxious. It brought anxiety to the participants, which could affect their job status, fear of acquiring the virus, fear of financial matters, and worry about the bills and budget. Many face stressful, frustrating, disturbing, disappointing, and sad challenges. The implication I could give is to administer Psychological First Aid for the employees given by an individual capable of reducing stress and assisting in a healthy recovery following a traumatic event. Having also a healthy routine can have a positive impact on their thoughts and feelings. For example, eating healthy meals, physical exercise (such as walking, stretching, running, and cycling), getting enough sleep, and doing things you are passionate about (World Health Organization 2013).

Frustrated. Due to the pandemic, most participants experience frustration because adaptation is complex, and they cannot complete tasks due to the changes with the available resources. They are also irritated by the possibility that they are virus carriers and become dissatisfied with their work. Therefore, they must step away for a few minutes to manage healthily and cope with pandemic frustration. Changing their surroundings, even for a few minutes, by going into the next room or stepping outside can help people get their emotions under control. Take a break and a calming breath (Hagedorn, Wattick & Olfert, 2022).

Disturbed. The pandemic may have brought many changes to how people live their life. With it, at times, the participants were mentally disturbed, scared of the virus's continued propagation, plagued by the parent's decision to continue education, and nervous that everyone might have the virus. Practice self-care. Prioritize a healthy lifestyle by eating healthy foods, getting plenty of sleep, and avoiding bad habits such as smoking, drugs, or alcohol. In addition, try relaxation techniques like deep breathing, mindfulness, or yoga to relieve stress (Lin, Liu, Li & Zhang, 2021).

Challenged. During the acute phase of the pandemic, participants were challenged with limited interaction and different modalities. Also, difficulties in collaborating with colleagues during crises affected the education sector. As a result, employees strive hard to come up with solutions. Furthermore, the study has shown simple coping behaviors of the employees to deal with this challenge, such as a healthy diet, not reading too much about COVID-19 news, following a healthy daily routine, and spending time outdoors. It can protect them against anxiety and depressive symptoms in times of coronavirus (Turale, Meechamnan, & Kunaviktikul, 2020).

Disappointed. Unfinished tasks, limited access to information, and embarrassment at having low computer literacy cause participants to feel disappointed and alter their lives. Practice gratitude and empathy. Focusing on what people are thankful for can help them recover from disappointment. Also, when people are disappointed in someone, remember that everyone struggles in their way (Sherman, Park, Salsman, Williams, Amick, Hudson & Simonton-Atchley, 2021).

Mixed Emotions. Both positive and negative emotions are experienced simultaneously by participants, who may feel tired, happy, challenged by the new normal, anxious, and stressed. However, they feel still blessed, happy but struggling with the spread of a virus, physically exhausted and fatigued, glad yet devastated by some changes, sick, mentally anxious but still hopeful. Activities developing soft skills and self-pleasure, like the Zumba dance activity, will help them to develop their body movement and relieve stress (Kaur, Singh, Arya & Mittal, 2020).

People need to be more productive. Feeling unproductive is a familiar sensation, but during the pandemic, participants felt much more unproductive with their job duties and responsibilities since there was no guarantee that the task and activities would be completed. They needed to be more energized by the rules and procedures to follow. Practicing mindfulness, keeping an eye on whether one's thoughts are overwhelmingly positive. People can develop the skill of being mindful of their surroundings to respond appropriately to co-workers. People control their actions, not the circumstances (Trzebinski, Cabanski & Czarnecka, 2020).

Sad. The COVID-19 epidemic had a tremendous effect on our lives. Many of us are confronting challenges that can be stressful. People felt sad for clients such as students and parents. The budget was cut short; People felt terrible about paying many bills since vacation leave needed to be converted into cash. People were worried due to financial difficulties and were sad about not achieving well at school. To deal with these challenges, being creative, like drawing, painting, and journaling can help people express their feelings and calm down. Write people's sad thoughts on paper and then tear them up. People could also channel their feelings through music, singing, or dancing (Hyland, Shevlin, McBride, Murphy, Karatzias, Bentall & Vallières, 2020).

Stressed. Stressful situations, like an infectious disease outbreak, cause different reactions in different people. As a result, it is common to feel a variety of emotions. Participants were anxious about starting classes, were tense about not knowing when the virus would be eliminated, and was anxious about the administration's rules. To manage these difficult times, sharing with others and social connections are critical to overall well-being. Sharing their feelings with family and friends is a great way to manage stress (Pfeifer, Heyers, Ocklenburg & Wolf, 2021).

Happy. Happiness comes when the employees can spend time with their families, be grateful for the new opportunities, and appreciate the admin's initiative to ensure that employees follow health and safety protocols to prevent exposure to viruses. Being grateful for our Lord's protection during this pandemic also makes them feel blessed. Being at ease makes them feel safer to stay at home and cheerful to become more understanding of the situation. Participants felt blessed that the employment status is still good, the school finds means to support the employees, nothing changed despite the challenges

brought about by the pandemic, and they are thankful to have work still. Employees should stay connected with their family, friends, and co-workers, take care of themselves all the time and manage their stress levels, such as implementing a new time management technique. Moreover, they must have a healthy lifestyle, and share thoughts that will help them strengthen their relationships, connect with other people, and build their resilience to cope with life's ups and downs. This positive view of life can help them in their relationships and work and inspire them to be more creative and take more chances (Petrovic, Murgas & Králik, 2021).

Grateful. During uncertain times like these, our faith might be challenged, and it can be hard to discern where God fits in our lives. Participants felt thankful for everything, became more appreciative of the value of life, grateful for the protection of the Lord, blessed for the support of family, and thankful for still having a job. Being grateful is more critical than ever in trying times. By practicing gratitude, we can better manage our negative emotions, cope with traumatic events, and feel better. More importantly, gratitude can help people's friends and family (Butler & Jaffe, 2021).

At Ease. The coronavirus encourages participants to feel more at ease staying at home, relieved that the school is not reducing staff, and are more comfortable working from home. In this pandemic, a collaboration between staff and administration is essential to find ways to keep the institution operating, and adopt to the new normal. They must maintain a daily routine, such as waking up at the same time every day, eating healthy meals, taking breaks from COVID-19 news and social media, being physically active, and having enough (Malouff, TerKonda, Knight, Perlman, Munipalli, Dudenkov & Buskirk, 2021).

Positive. The pandemic gives the participants a positive outlook to become more understanding of the situation, more open to opportunities, adjusted to the proper health protocol, keep on praying to survive, become more resourceful, choose to collaborate, help each other, and adjust to the online classes. A positive attitude remaining hopeful, and seeing the best even in difficult situations is a much healthier way to live. A positive attitude manifests in the following ways: being more optimistic, empathetic, understanding of others, and grateful for the good things in their work and life. They are approachable daily with an appreciative mindset (Khan & Shah, 2021).

Vigilant. The disease has been a part of our daily lives. Thus, wearing face masks and following health and safety protocols is necessary. Implementing these, the employees will help avoid contracting the virus by wearing facemasks and face shields, taking extra care of themselves, being more concerned about the family's health, and being vigilant of the people around them. They are encouraged and motivated to continue practicing the preventive measures to help keep the communities safe from the virus. Continuing these actions is the number one thing we can all do to reduce our chances of catching and spreading COVID-19 (Chae, Yip, Martz, Chung, Richeson, Hajat & LaVeist, 2021).

Employment is Still Good. Participants felt blessed that the job status is still good, the school found a method to help the staff, nothing changed despite the problems caused by the pandemic, and they are thankful to have work still. It is helpful to show appreciation and be respectful, honest, and supportive during this challenging time. Challenging and new tasks are also essential to maintain employee engagement, productivity, and motivation (Spurk & Straub, 2020).

Budget Became Necessary. The pandemic's effects on participants' finances are broadly indifferent from each other but learning some skills, including teaching them how to properly budget, being more cautious with their spending habits, and learning to save more money for an emergency fund is the key. Participants are willing to change to improve themselves and adjust to the new normal. Activities developing hard skills like managing finances that the participants will learn the correct way of managing their finances are good (Anessi-Pessina, Barbera, Langella, Manes-Rossi, Santino, Sicilia & Steccolini, 2020).

Convenient Lifestyle. Realizing that no matter how much time they think they have, at the end of the day, the participants value having spent more quality time with the family as appreciating life. Additionally, people said they preferred to study at home, thought it was the safest place to do so, and had access to webinars. Exercise and relaxation exercises can be helpful tools to keep them calm during this situation (Kolokotroni, Mosquera, Quattrocchi, Heraclides, Demetriou & Philippou, 2021).

Embrace Change. Perceived limitations in everyday life, the safety of everyone, and our daily routines during the pandemic phases have been drastically reduced. Participants learned to be open-minded, accepted the new typical scenario, and some everyday things in the past were no longer practiced to this date. Employees must maintain a positive attitude regardless of the new situation. It is always important to be optimistic and maintain a good attitude at work, and having an open-minded perspective will allow them to identify and grab these new opportunities. Employees find ways to adapt and adjust to the

outcomes of the pandemic, which helps them remember life changes and provides opportunities to reflect on what truly matters. This COVID-19 pandemic may be the universe's way of getting us to look within ourselves and identify what needs to change (Klatt, Bawa, Gabram, Blake, Steinberg, Westrick & Holliday, 2020).

Mentally Distracted. The COVID-19 pandemic significantly impacted our way of life. Many of us are dealing with complex and overwhelming challenges. Participants have reported feeling mentally disoriented during the pandemic, including increased anxiety about their surroundings, worry about getting sick, inability to concentrate on their work, worry about their finances, and fear of social interaction and going outside. It is natural to feel mentally distracted during the COVID-19 pandemic. However, there are ways that people can help themselves, others, and their community manage stress. Take breaks from news stories, including those on social media, take care of their body, make time to unwind, connect with others, and connect with their community or faith-based organizations (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2020).

Negativity Increased. Negative things came in when the participants experienced sadness, were mentally and emotionally disturbed, experienced many downfalls and their psychological and mental health was affected because of the pandemic. It may have brought many changes to their lives, such as uncertainty, altered daily routines, financial pressures, social isolation, worry about getting sick, how long the pandemic will last, whether their job will be influenced and what the future will bring. In addition, information overload, rumors, and misinformation can make their life feel out of control and make it unclear what to do. Being mindful of what people do and paying attention to the present moment will help cultivate their sense of being. The practice of mindfulness has been proven to help overcome anxiety, stress, and loneliness, especially during the tough times during the lockdown, and support need about how to combat negative thinking to reduce negative thoughts surpass this destructive mental impact brought by the COVID-19 pandemic (Sorokowski, Groyecka, Kowal, Sorokowska, Białek, Lebuda & Karwowski, 2020).

We adapted New Perspective. Adapting to the new usual way of life, primarily through technology, has completely transformed how we live, work, and learn. It affects each area of our everyday lives, and this new normal has transformed virtually overnight. Life adjustments can be tricky and bring on many experiences and emotions. Setting a routine can be helpful. In addition to doing their task, schedule time for their physical and emotional health, fun, creativity, social connection, and stress relief (Thomas, Suleman, Mackay, Hayer, Singh, Correll & Dursun, 2020).

Value Each Moment. The participants learned to cherish life and the people around them more, to live it to the fullest, and to take good care of their physical, mental, and emotional well-being. Team building activity will include various collective activities to enhance social relations and define team roles. The sense of accomplishment they will feel after overcoming obstacles will soar the team's morale. They will discover how having fun and accomplishing goals can be the best morale booster (Whillans, Perlow & Turek, 2021).

Implications for Future Research

The result of the study could not generate a generalization of the participants' experiences. Thus, a study of the same kind may be conducted with other research sites to validate the results. Furthermore, future research may be done to re-interview some of the study's participants to see their views, feelings, and the perceived effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on their lives. Determining the extent of the problem and providing intervention to address such, could be the other research direction to consider.

Concluding Remarks

As a result, this study may offer employees a new perspective and understanding of their experiences during the pandemic. The outcomes are also envisioned to uplift every employee to stay braver and calmer, fight for survival and stay positive amidst the COVID-19 pandemic.

Based on the study, being a guidance facilitator in a private organization, people have noticed that some employees suffered from different difficulties, such as health, safety, switching of work schedule, and were forced to adjust and cope with the challenges of the new normal. In addition, teachers are using different online platforms to engage students with other activities that contribute to their learning. Because of the study's result, we now know that even though the challenges amidst the pandemic are inevitable, opportunities always appear. Therefore, we could still look at the bright side and treat each challenge as an opportunity for growth and improvement. Furthermore, knowing the different experiences caused by the pandemic to every employee worldwide, specifically Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges employees, we could have a general view and perspective on how the pandemic affected their lives.

Additionally, in this time of the pandemic, the best lesson we have learned from this crisis should be the foundation and guidelines for us to move forward continuously. Moreover, it provides a clear path forward to mitigate the harm done and avert such harm in the future. Moreover, while we cannot avoid this pandemic, we can choose to counter its consequences and be prepared for future crises.

Finally, this research opens up opportunities for private institutions, employees, and administration to further hone their skills, maximizing their existing knowledge about their duties and responsibilities, incorporating the findings we learned during the pandemic.

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